

what's your problem

The Evaluation Report

June 2023

delivered by:

Problem area:
Mental Health
Support in Liverpool
City Region.

Supported by:

P2

what's inside?

A BIT OF BACKGROUND

OUR APPROACH

WHAT WE DISCOVERED

OUR RECOMMENDATIONS

OUR FINAL THOUGHTS

APPENDIX

P3

P8

P20

P27

P35

P37

P3

a bit of background

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What's Your Problem 2023 was the second iteration of an innovative programme committed to finding data-driven solutions to some of Liverpool City Region's (LCR) biggest challenges.

Delivered in partnership between the Civic Data Cooperative (CDC) and Capacity, this year's programme specifically focussed on men at risk of suicide and isolation in students. By working jointly with CDC, Capacity was able to listen and engage with key stakeholders across the region to gather insights and start some solution-based thinking of how best to use civic data to create better public and third sector experiences for the communities affected by them.

Recognising the complex nature of this challenge area and the fact that public services are often disconnected - we designed this programme with a commitment to better

understanding the problem from a variety of perspectives. Drawing out insight after careful listening and engagement with sector experts, service providers, partner organisations and those with lived experience we developed a programme which provided space for collaboration and opportunity to build a network of stakeholders. This wasn't just about opening doors between the sectors; it was about taking them off the hinges.

The picture of mental health support is varied and complex, with people working hard to successfully make improvements in this area for decades - we know there is no one size fits all 'solution'. However, we often design

solutions to complex problems through one or a few similar perspectives and we hoped that this programme would encourage new ways of working, creating a space to talk honestly about the scale of these challenges, bring together as many different perspectives as possible and to really get under the skin of the problems.

We created an honest and collaborative brief around what isn't working between innovators and the public sector to help nurture ideas and broaden partnerships in an honest and organic way.

The key project aims:

Create space for a deep understanding of the challenge area, gathering intelligence on the wellbeing challenge as informed by sector experts.

Create and connect a network of brilliant people with ideas about how to solve the issues in this space.

Support this network to develop a viable and scalable solution for LCR that can tackle the challenges in mental health

Delivered through a series of events and support sessions, the programme resulted in the award of funding to LCR SMEs Gigmate and The Mind Map to further develop their business models and data innovation plans. Whilst not entirely as envisaged at the outset, the funding will enable them to enhance their use of data whilst further developing solutions which contribute towards tackling the immediate mental health challenges that the LCR faces.

The purpose of this evaluation is to capture all approaches taken, alongside our successes and areas of improvement for the programme.

Let's look at the context

What's Your Problem 2023 is part of the wider strategic vision and aims of both CDC and LCR Combined Authority contributing towards:

Positioning CDC as connector and creator around using data to transform how we support communities.

Understanding what data and insights tell us and how these can be applied to affect change.

Influencing key stakeholders about using this way of working when designing services.

Engaging with SMEs across the region and, ultimately, increasing employment in the longer term.

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a bit of background

Our Programme Timeline

And with that, the Civic Data Cooperative's 'What's your problem?' series was created:

‘Creating a space to talk honestly about the scale of these challenges, bring together as many different perspectives as possible and to really get under the skin of the problems.’

our approach

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our approach

WYP was co-created with our key stakeholders. This delivered a programme which was informed, considered and that tapped into the needs of all the points of view from within and across the siloed public service and SME communities.

The programme had 3 key phases, expert engagement, SME support and event delivery. This allowed us to create a large network of stakeholders which was crucial in establishing the collaborative nature of the programme, bringing people together who wouldn't normally connect – but who often shared a first-hand experience of the problem areas.

GATHERING EXPERT INSIGHTS (November 2022 – January 2023):

We had detailed conversations with 30 sector experts to get under the skin of the challenges they were seeing in men's and student's mental health. Focussed at a regional level, research consistently revealed the extent to which men's and student wellbeing was a significant challenge faced by many front-line services, specifically working with Higher Educational Institutions (HEI), General Practice (GP), Public Health (PH) and the third sector. These expert insights helped us to refine the brief ahead of the problem pick up event. Insights we gathered through this phase included:

56%

of men were living with fear or anxiety

STUDENTS

What students often need is someone to talk to, kindness and listening to work through practical things."

Data isn't shared between NHS Trusts [and support organisations] locally or nationally."

MEN

48% of men said their mental health had worsened because of the pandemic."

For a full list of organisations consulted, please refer to Appendix A

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Shaped by the experts we spoke with we developed our focussed problem areas as the basis of the 'problem pick-up'. The 2 refined problem areas were:

MEN:
Support
before suicide

STUDENTS:
Connection
before Crisis

MEN:
Support
before suicide

Protecting men’s mental health following life-changing events: We need to support men to recognise when something in their life doesn’t feel right. It’s critical to increase the likelihood of men connecting with something that helps before reaching crisis point. Often this can be linked to key life events such as redundancy, parenthood, divorce, and health scares - we want to focus on activating the natural touchpoints that could make a difference earlier, particularly if the person can’t see a mental health challenge ahead.

1.46 million

men were referred to NHS talking therapies in 20/21 for common mental health needs.

71%

of suspected suicides are men*

Men are

2-3x

less likely to report a mental health concern to an appropriate professional or support service compared to women.

Why was this chosen?

- The numbers show us that male suicide is increasing.
- Experts told us that men often sought help before suicide, but not from traditional mental health services. As a result, they often didn’t get the help they needed.
- How could we reach these men when they reach out for help and connect them to mental health support?

There’s a variety of problems upstream and downstream. Upstream there’s this lack of connectivity and cohesion across communities. There’s a lot of organisations that live in that community space, but we don’t do enough of the collaboration stuff, we do too much of the competition stuff. Lots of organisations have really good intentions but they are all doing the same stuff or competing against each other for the same pots of money. It’s through no bad intentions, it’s just the way the system is set up. We also overlook the strengths that exist in communities already and focus too much on what’s wrong rather than what’s strong... further upstream we have difficulties accessing services, excessive waiting lists, inefficiencies and ineffectiveness in services, one size fits all blanket approaches.”

– Founder First Person Project CIC

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STUDENTS: Connection before Crisis

Joining the dots across mental health support for students. There is an abundance of places for students to go for support, advice, and activities. However, the connection between organisations, digital tools and information is hit and miss. We want to make it simpler to share intelligence, to join up support pathways and to identify opportunities for stronger preventative support.

20%

Around 1 in 5 students experience a mental health problem in the UK... that's around:

5 million people.

80%

increase in need for student 'Nightline' support since 2020

20%

of the student population are international students with

47%

self-reporting a current mental health issue*

student minds

Why was this chosen?

- Students would often seek help from a number of support agencies ranging from HEIs, GPs, A&E, and Community mental health teams whilst at university, then connect back with services at home in between term time meaning students have to retell their story multiple times.
- Despite services trying their best to support, they are working in silo with no picture of what other help is being given to individual students where there is a lack of data connectivity between organisations.
- Effective commissioning: it is impossible to tell which services are having an impact and ultimately may result in duplication of services.

DEVELOPING INTELLIGENCE BANKS January 2023

To support the programme, the team developed an 'Intelligence Bank', collating a range of sources which could be accessed by anyone. This included numerous datasets, insight reports, useful links and widely recognised research that provides a deeper level of insight for programme participants. These Intelligence Banks became a central repository for all resources connected to the programme. They were 'live' with participants both drawing from and adding to the collective knowledge within.

The majority of this data, intelligence and knowledge will create a foundation for the CDC's Data Commons. This will help to paint the national and local picture of mental health data and intelligence. Using this approach will frame some of the knottiest problems in this area and ultimately contribute to solution thinking.

We wanted to build on our understanding and get to know the work already happening to address the issues and, begin to frame the system wide challenges so they could be understood by SMEs looking to generate solutions. We wanted to be inclusive of SMEs and VCSEs who perhaps already had experience of working or providing services in mental health support, but also give enough data, information and intelligence for SMEs who were less familiar with this space to digest existing intelligence from across the public and third sectors.

The Intelligence Banks were really useful, you can tell how much time and effort went into bringing all that information together, no one ever does that. I've downloaded them all and I'll probably look back over those again and again."

– SME applicant to the programme

a quick guide to this year's intelligence bank

resource	description	hyp
Liverpool City Council	Ward-by-ward Liverpool City Council data. Variety of socio-economic, health and environmental factors including comparable mental wellbeing data.	LCC Ward
ONS: Cost of Living and Wellbeing (Oct 2022)	ONS reports and data dashboard outlining snapshot research undertaken in October 2022. Key statistics and insight into increased cost of living and adverse impact on specific demographics.	Office for National Statistics
Research Papers	Academic research primarily focussed on isolation and loneliness amongst post-graduate students. Suggests the underreported figure of poor mental health amongst post-graduates with the focus placed on undergraduates.	Research P
Student Services Partnerships: Toolkit	Toolkit for service managers and practitioners to develop partnerships responding to student Mental health needs.	SPEDS

Students are often registered with a different GP at university, meaning life-long data is less common.

20% Around 1 in 5 students experience a mental health problem in the UK... that's around 5 million people

The reported rate of men with common mental health problems stands at 13.2% official figures show men are two to three times less likely to report a mental health concern to an appropriate professional or support service compared to women.

1 in 4 of those who reported difficulty paying their energy bills experienced moderate to severe depressive symptoms, which is nearly three times higher than those who found it easy to pay their energy bills

Key research suggests the key barriers preventing men from accessing support are:

- Self-reliance and meeting societal expectation (traditional expectations of masculinity) Adoption of coping strategies prior to seeking assistance (such as alcohol or substance misuse or suppression of emotions)
- Embarrassment and denial, attempting to meet societal expectations
- Poor health literacy resulting in not recognising or acknowledging symptoms
- Distrust and perception of the healthcare system with the stigma around mental health

Siddell, A. L., Seaton, J. S. and Nelson, N. A. (2011) Mental health stigma: Impact on mental health treatment attitudes and physical health. Journal of Health Psychology

The Problem Pick-Up Event

February 2023

Launched at the Bluecoat in early February, our Problem Pick-up Event brought together stakeholders from across sectors to share perspectives and insights. The event sought to:

1. Spend time opening doors between these sectors, coming together to really pull apart some of the market gaps.
2. Delve into some of the key challenges public sector leaders currently face so that innovations have a solid ground and insight for new product development

Hear from our event host Mark'

The best thing about has been the older guy that said 'this has been the most honest and amazing conversation we've had in this sector for 40 years'... I go home happy, that was incredible."

- Host, Problem Pick-up Event

The event was highly successful and attended by 96 stakeholders from across the VCSE, public and private sectors. There was a consensus throughout the day that there is a real passionate energy to tackle these issues, and a recognition of the pressing and real impact of poor mental health on people and communities through LCR.

This event is important for two reasons: Number one - co-creation and co-ideation, it's the future. For one person to be sat in a room making decisions and having ideas, it ain't going to work. There are three ways of having better ideas; one - ask better questions, this did that, two - speak to people who are not like you, this did that, three - meditate, feed the brainwave... we didn't do that, but we could do that! The process was magic. Number two - the two issues we've looked at are massive and they are getting bigger. These are really big challenges that we face, and we are applying new techniques, it's the only game in town."

- Host, Problem Pick-up Event

The opportunity to meet and hear from people working in these areas of interest, and those with lived experiences were so insightful. As a freelancer it is hard to justify setting aside time and money to attend events like this, but I found it hugely beneficial. I am easily pleased with pens and notebooks, but in reality, I really enjoyed the whole event. I thought it was brilliantly organised with warm and welcoming staff, that facilitated the groups really well, especially in such a short space of time. Nice moments of networking happened naturally during refreshment time, which was an added bonus."

- Entrepreneur stakeholder

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A select panel of experts with different perspectives of the men and student challenges opened the event (with representation from CHAMPS, First Person Project CIC, University of Liverpool Student Support Services Lead and Brownlow GP), illustrating and introducing the challenge areas and the complexities and perspectives of organisations who are confronted daily with the challenge areas.

Breaking off into smaller groups to allow more detailed discussion, public sector leaders, contributors and businesses talked candidly about what was already being done, what was not being addressed and where there were opportunities to change and improve. The groups identified 7 key areas of insight (outlined in Insights section) where there was a collective view that energy should be focused.

A quick feel
of the event

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The conversations and rich insight of the event were fully distilled into seven key themes and then refined into three key briefs:

TIMES OF CHANGE

We all experience significant life events, from starting university or becoming a parent or separating from a long-term partner. As people deal with life events and the feelings that come with them, they need to find ways to cope.

How do we better reach and support people who are struggling with their experience of significant life events and what's the role of powerful human connection in helping people manage that change?

One of the biggest things that we can do to ensure good mental health is to maximise healthy connection with others, and by forming positive relationships we can find someone to lean on as we adapt to change.

CONFUSING THE ISSUE

Whilst stigma and discrimination about mental health continues to exist, we know this has lessened over recent years. The terms 'mental health' and 'wellbeing' are often used interchangeably and our familiarity with them has broadened our conversations.

The two are connected but they're actually very different. Insight shows us that this merged description can confuse people – meaning they're unsure when and where to reach out for help.

For some people this means their mental health condition feels downplayed as it's put in the 'wellbeing and selfcare' box, and by contrast, for others their experience of a few challenging days can lead to a request for formal mental health support.

How can we help people to make enough sense of their thoughts and feelings so that they can connect to the right type of help and support, for their particular needs at a time they need it?

SHARING AND CARING

Many students are well tuned into what mental health support is available to them. This might include university services, their GP, and A&E, but also extends to community-based support and self-help tools.

Once the academic term is over and the majority of students head home, the lack of joined-up system connectivity means there is a need to constantly retell their story and possibly engage with a new form of support.

This problem is not new in healthcare and many projects and organisations are working to join up key data. How can we make improvements around how we collect and securely share data, manage risk across partnerships and/or better measure and report on outcomes for student mental health?

The Shaping Sessions

February - April 2023

To support organisations in shaping an application in response to these refined briefs. The programme offered a series of sessions. These were designed to build upon the connections made at the first event and to make sure those interested in the programme had a regular touch point and communication.

These sessions included:

1-2-1 Support Sessions

The first stage of support post-launch event was a 30-minute 1-2-1 consultation and advice session. This was offered so potential applicants could discuss their idea with a member of the Capacity and CDC team, to help further understand the brief and what the application should look to include. All 10 attendees of these advice sessions applied to the programme, including the eventual recipients of funding.

Data Shaping Session

This was an online workshop delivered by CDC which provided further support to SMEs, giving them a chance to think about their understanding of data and how it can be used in innovation. 20 attended the session which delved into a technical yet important area, in which the later recommendations consider. It revealed how many organisations are not always aware of how data can be used in a variety of ways and has the potential to enhance solutions.

Experts Shaping Session

Based online this was an opportunity for applicants to hear from and consult with sector experts on their idea and application, as well as making connections between different services in the mental health space. Experts at the session included commissioners in Mental Health services and the Integrated Care Board (ICB), a Mental Health Clinical Lead from ORCHA, representatives from the University of Liverpool student services and CHAMPS. 15 attended with the majority applying to the programme, using this opportunity to connect into a wider network of stakeholders.

Social Shaping Session

Harnessing our commitment to a collaborative programme, the social session was a networking event hosted in-person at The Reader Restaurant and Bar. Across the delivery of the programme, we heard from participants that meeting other people in this space was incredibly valuable, and often lead to sparking an idea or talking a problem through. This session provided participants the opportunity to support their application (attendance of Innovation Agency UK and Baltic Ventures) and with 21 attendees was able to encourage organic, in-depth quality conversations between those who have been involved in the programme.

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The Applications & Problem Pitch Event May 2023

SMEs submitted their application as a pitch deck or 15-minute video which was required to answer 14 questions about their organisation and innovation.

The programme received a total of 14 applications from SMEs, individuals and organisations across the mental health sector. Evaluated by senior members of the CDC and Capacity team, selected applications were chosen to move forward to the pitch event - an invitation to present their idea to a panel of experts and move closer to the seed funding award. Applicants who submitted an EOI but did not make it through to this final stage were each offered the opportunity to speak directly with a member of the team for feedback on their application as well as connections to other relevant services, stakeholders and/or SME business support.

Hosted at Baltic Creative, the pitch event was designed to bring together the most promising applicants and industry leaders to evaluate, challenge and contribute to SME's thinking. SME's were invited to pitch to a panel of experts which included representatives from the LCR Combined Authority, Mental Health Research for Innovation Centre (MRIC), Innovation Agency, Merseycare, Universities UK, CIPHA and Brownlow GP as well as members of the CDC and Capacity team.

Continuing the regular support and touchpoints that we provided for organisations throughout the programme, the event also included wrap-around support in the form of expert impact advice. We had heard from participants in the earlier Shaping Sessions that impact understanding and measurement was an area often alien to or unexplored by innovators, which informed the support offer at the pitch event. Each shortlisted SME took part in a 1-2-1 impact workshop delivered by Capacity's Impact Manager.

Captured through interviews on the day, there was a recognition of the support available to organisations to strengthen their approach, as well as the opportunity to connect with others in the industry who could help to further the impact beyond the programme:

The day resulted in the award of funding to The Mind Map and Gigmate, both of whom pitched an exciting innovative solution in response to the problem areas. Both organisations received an initial grant award of £10,000 to increase capacity for further development of solutions, commercial models, impact thinking and data innovation.

[Today has been] not transactional. It's very much a conversation and collaboration... I've thought about data in a different way, I've done a great session about impact with Aroa. It was a real eye opener for me...I want to unpack this a little bit more...Even being in the pitch room just then I was like, 'even if I am not successful, I've kind of got somewhere here because I am being taken seriously by a lot of people with big brains.'

– SME finalist to the programme

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what we discovered

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What's Your Problem 2023 has provided important insight into the key issues around mental health and wellbeing in LCR and built connection across public and private sector spaces and between providers. It delved deeper into the overarching areas, building intelligence that confronts the current picture of mental health support and illustrates the passion and commitment of organisations and individuals living and working in LCR.

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what we learnt about student and men's mental health

Our problem pick-up event gave us seven key areas of interest that the community in LCR wanted to address and think about solutions for.

The 7 key themes were:

1. EARLY INTERVENTION AND AWARENESS:

Individuals don't have the tools they need to recognise and manage their mental wellbeing, and may not realise they need support before crisis, we need to be unblocking ways to connect with these people and signpost into support as a need develops. We have come a long way in understanding and identifying mental health but there is a continual need to educate and inform from a young age.

We struggle to identify where individuals are balancing normal life stress and expectations against a need for mental health support. Where getting help from the system is required, navigating that complex system is difficult to do alone or do well. Often. Communities of support show real success when tackling these issues – we shouldn't focus too much on the individual but on the structures that exist for young people and men can get support within their local community, backed up with an evidence base to target interventions better.

We should recognise we have some brilliant solutions, but they need scaling to meet increased demand; a difficult challenge when resources are finite and other difficulties building resource need unblocking.

2. DISCONNECTION BETWEEN SERVICES:

In many ways, mental health support has come a long way in recent years and there is now a smorgasbord of services on offer set up to address one or several issues at a time. This means individuals might be seeking help and support from a number of places or services, but behind this is a lumpy provision which doesn't connect up around a person; we are seeing their needs through lots of different lenses, rather than as one complete story. Across this landscape, data is siloed in different systems or out of date and we aren't using the intelligence that lies within it. How could we understand what the best thing is for an individual when it's not possible to measure what is and isn't working across lots of touchpoints?

There is a lack of collaboration between organisations within a competitive funding market where there is no option for collaborative funding models between service provisions. Models of support on offer also have room to grow, where some services are accessible at the wrong times of day for the greatest need, with many services open during the day, but little on offer in the evening and weekend. As the support is difficult to navigate, it is difficult to get a full picture of what is available and where the gaps need to be plugged. Amongst disparate systems and operating models there are services which need to be adapted or integrated, for this to be most effective we need a more collaborative way of contracting and investing between organisations with statutory responsibility for providing this support.

3. HOW DO WE LISTEN TO PEOPLE WELL?

Statutory services have existed for a long time, but the rigid frameworks of how they operate have not changed with demand. Within these structures, time is often spent with people who aren't able to listen well or carry out effective connections into services, with no one place taking responsibility for an individual's complete needs.

Risk dominates the need for assigning resource where we should be identifying the best people to actively listen to during assessments, to gain a clearer picture of the person or their individual needs.

Alongside this we collect a lot of data, but we don't really understand what it is telling us or using it well to offer help to those who need it. In a world where this data was manipulated better, we would be empowered to take information, identify those at risk and make it easier to access support where there are early signs of need.

4. LIFE TRANSITIONS:

Big life events come in many shapes and sizes, from starting university, becoming parents or losing a loved one, but we are often not prepared for these changes. These big life events leave people without a network and familiar reference points. There is a lack of coping mechanisms and a gap in understanding that we might be experiencing low mood/poor wellbeing due to a number of societal factors.

How do we prevent escalation in daunting moments? We need to adjust to be able to cope in a positive way that doesn't result in poorer outcomes. Wrapped around this there is an opportunity to utilise technology better, connect into supportive networks and communities and signpost efficiently between services, where systems and connectivity have become an essential part of wellbeing support outside of traditional institutions and health care.

5. TIPPING LIFESTYLE ADVICE INTO ACTION:

Seeking help in a system with endless options can cause paralysis, and we can't forget about people who don't realise they need support and aren't seeking help. We need ways of using the data to connect people to the right help at the right time and better ways of finding people who are struggling alone to deliver support that is tailored and sensitive.

People starting on a journey of support will be at different stages of readiness to engage and need to be connected to the right service at the right time. Lifestyle 'medicine' takes time and energy to get right and might mean failing at some attempts along the way. Obvious lifestyle changes might not feel possible to an individual at a given moment, but we should spend more time connecting as humans and listening to what a person needs to co-create positive change in a noisy landscape.

Coupled with this, our statutory services should be better empowered to connect individuals to support and help that is right for them and not limited to a 'set menu'.

what we discovered

6. SOCIAL EXPECTATIONS ('PERFECT LIFE SYNDROME'):

Over time and under the influence of rapid technology infrastructure improvement and increased exposure to social media we have seen people and society change beyond recognition. Today we are changing constantly. Our real lives often cannot measure up to the expectations that we have set ourselves based on what we see around us. We look at other people through a filter and consider them to have a 'perfect life', leading to dissatisfaction with our own circumstances.

This requires solutions which recognise change and change alongside the 'problem' itself. Services should be designed to adapt and change over time, and we should value a 'life-course' approach to mental wellbeing.

Progressive social change sits at the heart of managing and coping with signs of poor mental health, but this is often put in the 'too hard to do' box as the ripples of social change flow far from statutory services and into the global economy.

7. SYSTEM DATA LINKING:

Support for students doesn't provide positive outcomes due to the complexity of siloed systems collecting data. Within these systems an individual's data is not aggregated and data IP and data sharing is complex and carries perceived risk. Students in particular move between multiple systems as they change city frequently throughout the academic year, whilst often using various platforms to support mental wellbeing.

This complexity means students have to re-tell their story to professionals who are only seeing part of the picture. Over time this also means that continuation of care is poor and providers don't have accurate intelligence to help plan and shape services, where individuals are receiving multiple levels of support which is unhelpful in managing mental health and duplicated spend.

Scan above to view the video

what we learnt about how to run the programme

1. IN-PERSON EVENTS CREATED THE MOST EFFECTIVE INSIGHTS

The face-to-face nature of the event boasted a good energy and created an opportunity for great networking. Getting people who have a passion for tackling the big challenges in the same room was brilliant, reflected in some of the feedback from the day...

2. CONNECTION AND SUPPORT WERE VALUED AND RESULTED IN APPLICATIONS.

The frequent support sessions and communication throughout the programme were valued with the support sessions and opportunities to connect, discuss and review ideas prior to application felt to be beneficial.

3. THERE ARE ON-GOING CHALLENGES TO INCREASE INVOLVEMENT FROM UNDER-REPRESENTED COMMUNITIES.

Despite the number of applications, our diversity and inclusion monitoring showed that there was a lack of applicants from under-represented communities, with all applications received focussed on general mental health and wellbeing rather than targeting a specific underrepresented group. 66% of the anonymous respondents were white males, with only one respondent identifying as disabled. Addressed in the recommendations, there is a further need to centre the programme that makes it accessible for communities within and beyond the broader categories of men at risk of suicide

and students – such as communities that are more isolated or considering the mental health of international students. Feedback suggests that more could also be done to ensure that people’s lived experience perspectives have prominence in future:

[People with experience of poor] physical and emotional health need to give their input to this work... it’s important we understand their perspective of what’s lacking”.

- SME stakeholder

We’ve heard from lots of people that this is the first opportunity to speak to someone on the ‘other side’; it’s surprising that those conversations haven’t happened in the past so being able to provide the space for that to happen is great.”

- Programme Manager, Civic Data Cooperative

The value in the community was huge. Conversations shape change and the shared goal approach is commendable.”

- SME applicant to the programme

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4. THE PROGRAMME NEEDS TO MAINTAIN FLEXIBILITY TO RESPOND ORGANICALLY.

Whilst the programme set out to find solutions that are innovative in their use of data, and how they could potentially change the way data is used by organisations at a regional level.

Applications, and the organisations that eventually received funding, were rooted in front-line service delivery. Although not intended for the programme and not an inherently negative point, it meant that the programme invested in solutions that required further support and development before they could reach a stage of cutting-edge data innovation. Both recipients of funding were asked to further develop the assessment of commercial viability as well as the plan for the role of data in their product.

This is an important insight for how we deliver the next iteration of the programme. The programme should better articulate that solutions must demonstrate data innovation and how to use data differently, rather than attaching it to an already-formed front-line service.

Connected to this, the majority of applications to this year's programme were for business-as-usual services, which the programme cannot fund. The use of data was often presented in these applications, however, they did not align well with the programme briefs or were not innovative in their approach.

It's clear that organisations operating in the mental health field are struggling to fund core business components, with some organisations being fully transparent about the need to find core funding from new places.

In addition, some applicants needed additional support in order to effectively respond to the assessment questions, demonstrate well-thought-out financial proposals, robust market analysis or a strong business case. Much of this support already exists in the region, but it is clear that the businesses engaging with this problem need signposting to this provision.

our recommendations

delivered by:

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across the system

1. Use the insights gathered and the momentum and energy developed to inform wider opportunities beyond the programme.

The programme lifted the lid on some of the most difficult problems in the LCR mental health landscape, generating new insights and putting people with energy, experience and drive together to find ways forward – there was a clear appetite to increase the wider impact of this network beyond the programme.

We need to build on these insights and share them with researchers, service designers and commissioners of mental health services to inform current planning and future delivery. The development of the Mental Health Research for Innovation Centre (MRIC) provides a key opportunity to do this.

As well as the specific learnings, there is potential to design future programmes which create space to better understand the market in which the problem sits, investing in creating connections in this space as early as possible.

What will MRIC do?

The University of Liverpool and Mersey Care NHS Foundation Trust have teamed up to create the Mental Health Research for Innovation Centre (M-RIC). Our ground-breaking research facility based in Liverpool will impact directly on NHS mental health services.

Our aim is simple, to improve mental healthcare for all patients and service users. We will do this by making Liverpool a world leader in learning better mental healthcare systematically from research embedded in care.

NHS
Mersey Care
NHS Foundation Trust

2. Continue to build support for SMEs throughout the programme and signpost to other support networks.

WYP focusses on accelerating early-stage innovation ,however this year's programme saw many entries apply for core business funding, or operational running costs. We need to be more explicit about what we are expecting and how much we will offer financially.

Where organisations do need core business funding, we should use our strong understanding of their product and business, developed through their involvement in the programme, in order to successfully signpost them to alternative support solutions and make tailored introductions.

Scan the QR code for the full video

across the programme: What's your problem?

1. *The central role of data in the programme needs to be articulated more clearly at the outset.*

It's clear that for many of the submissions into the programme, data was an afterthought, rather than being front and centre to an idea. The next iteration of the programme should:

- Clearly articulate the data problem with emphasise on the CDC mission e.g., how data can work better for residents in LCR as well as how organisations can feed into collective data across a range of issues such as health, housing, air quality and environment.
- Deliver data innovation workshops early in the programme so applicants are clear on expectations and how to frame their idea around using data innovatively.
- Feedback on the 'Intelligence Banks' is good, but we should question what role the intelligence from these files is playing in generating ideas within the programme and if this is muddying the definition of data.

- CDC need to be upfront about what their role is on providing access to or support with data or supporting data innovation. This could be done through a number of methods:
 - Refining business case need with SMEs, supported by existing data.
 - Mentoring
 - The Data Commons, which is currently in development by the CDC will provide a sandpit area in the design for people to access and explore the data.

our recommendations

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2. Keep networking and connecting people at the heart of the programme, increasingly encouraging collaboration and partnership from the launch event to the programme end.

The programme should continue to create space for honest, productive conversations that challenge a problem from more than one perspective. People have valued:

- The connections made and honest conversations, but we need to strengthen the connection to the market to troubleshoot earlier.
- Sector experts should remain closely involved and updated throughout the programme so they can help to shape applications and provide frequent constructive and honest insight.
- Both years of the programme have seen positive reactions and brought great energy to events, particularly where these events have been in-person.
- We need to recognise that engagement can get lost in the middle part of the programme for those not looking to pitch and consider ways to ensure continued engagement and relevant opportunities.

We have had a brilliant response to the programme and have an opportunity to drive deeper by working more closely with system leaders. We want to see a stronger presence of the system gatekeepers; commissioners, decision-makers and the ICB need to be around the table so this insight can move beyond understanding and into action. The dream would see local system sponsorship of solutions, nurturing the development of the solution and adopting it across the region.

3. Be clear about what we mean by innovation and rule out ideas early that are not aligned with the challenge areas.

Future iterations of the project need to be clearer about what sort of solutions we are looking for and braver about ruling out ideas that don't fit the programme brief. This should set the expectation of what sort of solutions cannot be funded by the programme but also be realistic about what stage of maturity an idea should be at to allow space to recognise what business support or partnership is necessary to move innovation forward.

On a practical level, the Microsoft Forms applications used in the 2021-2022 programme ensured that SMEs articulated all key elements. The pitch deck or video option left too much space for scope creep and meant that entrants were not focused on answering the question.

Future iterations of the programme should:

Provide further 1-2-1 expert advice and support to help SMEs troubleshoot problems and have honest conversations about their market positioning. This will require further commitment from 'experts'.

Expand the programme or partner to include more time to support SMEs to create clearer, more confident and thought-out pitches, which cover the key areas experts want to see, including but not limited to:

- What is your innovation?
- What is the role of data?
- Funding ask; what money do need and - how will you spend it?
- Full market analysis
- Refined business case

Consider a revised programme structure which builds the necessary support and provides greater scope for collaboration. Rather than the existing project phases, following the expert shaping session and launch event, we could enhance the shaping, application and pitch stages in order to work more closely with a select few organisations with a promising idea, feeding in partners to collaborate with, giving more time to the development of impactful innovations in response to the brief.

In short this could look like:

1 week to submit and expression of interest following the launch event.

A series of tailored support interactions and sessions to develop ideas connecting stakeholders and partners.

Promising ideas apply for exploration timing and support.

Additional conversations to establish and provide support needed for a strong pitch and connecting to existing support in the region.

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4. Sow the seed of collaboration from the start and develop an approach that focuses more on co-creation.

Recognising that people responding to the programme are usually early stage in their thinking. This programme can give time, space and expertise. Let's be bold about co-creation next time and work hand in hand with shortlisted organisations to give longer opportunity to evolve ideas. Nurturing these relationships will take time, so thought should be given to the best way to take SMEs through the process in the most nurturing, efficient and productive way possible, where we matchmake potential partners and give them time and space to work through an idea and sign-post others to business support in the region.

We know that some efforts to collaborate didn't result in a submission and we recognise that joint delivery and development is hard where organisations are competing in the market. To do this well we need a longer runway to facilitate and organise SMEs around real innovation with real resources, time and structure to allow meaningful co-production and design.

5. Align the values and strategy of the CDC to the programme.

The CDC is now an established stakeholder in the region, with a clear identity and way of working which the programme needs to reflect, including:

- The storytelling about CDC should be consistent throughout the programme, to do this we should link the messaging about the programme to the existing strategy. We should seek to understand:
 - Our audience: who are we speaking to and how are we positioning ourselves?
 - Our purpose: what are we trying to say through our social posts and activity? Why?
 - Spending time in preparation for the programme gathering a fuller picture of the sector, still focussing on expert insights but undertake more market research to understand the data and technology in this space.

- Need to have a deeper and more committed approach to diversity and inclusion, leaning on experts in this space e.g., Kindred and The Women's Organisation and beyond, into the wider part of LCR.
- Keeping and developing an operational commitment to using socially trading organisations across LCR for event planning and delivery such as use of Baltic Creative, The Reader and Bluecoat

our final thoughts

The energy and passion of all of those involved in the programme has been phenomenal. We are confident that we have framed the right questions, opening up a diverse discussion about the best ways to tackle our region's mental health challenges – cutting across silos, and opening doors for a wide spectrum of people to connect and understand before diving into solutions. By involving the feedback from stakeholders at each stage of the programme we have pulled together the SME, public and VCSE sectors as mutual partners.

It's clear that there is a wealth of experience and passion in the LCR and that there are many existing organisations and initiatives which are delivering impact and improving the lives of thousands of individuals every day. However, many of these need additional financial support to deliver front-line services and as many SMEs with good ideas and innovations that they are keen to develop but need signposting, seed funding and business support if they are to realise their appetite to make change.

The programme has given us significant insight into the mental health landscape which future iterations of this programme and other new regional initiatives such as MRIC can use to continue to propel forward research and innovation.

CDC and Capacity are uniquely positioned to co-design collaborative projects such as this. With the learning we have developed from WYP 1 & 2 we have developed a working methodology which can be applied to the region's biggest problems – unlocking the ability of citizens to lead the solution development with data, intelligence, research and impact management at the core.

appendix

Appendix A: Summary of Engagement Stakeholders – Expert consultation

TYPE OF ORGANISATION

WHO?

Universities and HEIs

University of Liverpool
 Liverpool John Moores
 Liverpool Hope
 LIPA
 University of Sheffield
 Universities UK

Public Bodies

Merseycare
 Halton Borough Council
 Coroner’s Court

SMEs and VCSE

Open Door Charity
 Decently
 Health Junction
 LCVS
 Bolton Manbassadors
 Everton in the Community
 Wirral Mind

Supported by:

@LivUni

@LpoolCityRegion

Thanks for taking the time to read this report, if you would like any more information about the project, or to find out how to get involved in 2024, please get in touch with our team:

Ellie Fielding
Project Lead, Civic Data Cooperative
E.Fielding@liverpool.ac.uk

Emma Lord
Project Lead, Capacity
emma.lord@thisiscapacity.co.uk

delivered by:

